

CODEN [USA] : IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at : <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF SUPPOSITORIES
CONTAINING ANTI-FUNGAL DRUGS LOADED WITH
NANOPARTICLES**Deepika KG*¹, Dr Josephine Leno Jenita¹

Department Of Pharmaceutics

College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Dayananda Sagar University.

Abstract:

The development of effective antifungal therapies remains a critical challenge in medical science, particularly for patients with localized fungal infections. This study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of suppositories containing antifungal drugs incorporated with nanoparticles to enhance therapeutic efficacy and bioavailability. The research involved the preparation of suppositories using a range of antifungal agents, such as ketoconazole and fluconazole, which were loaded onto nanoparticles to improve drug release and absorption. Various nanoparticle carriers, including liposomes and polymeric nanoparticles, were utilized to optimize drug delivery. The suppositories were formulated through a process of melting and molding, ensuring uniform distribution of the active ingredients. Comprehensive evaluations included physicochemical characterization, drug release studies, and antifungal efficacy tests. Results demonstrated that the incorporation of nanoparticles significantly improved the solubility and stability of the antifungal drugs, leading to enhanced bioavailability and prolonged release profiles. The antifungal activity of the nanoparticle-loaded suppositories was superior compared to traditional formulations, suggesting a promising approach for treating localized fungal infections. This study highlights the potential of nanoparticle-enhanced suppositories in advancing antifungal therapy, offering a targeted and efficient treatment modality for patients.

Corresponding author:**Deepika KG, M.Pharm**

Department Of Pharmaceutics

College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Dayananda Sagar University.

deepikateju2000@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press **Deepika KG et al., Formulation And Evaluation Of Suppositories Containing Anti-Fungal Drugs Loaded With Nanoparticles, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (09).**

INTRODUCTION:

In the realm of healthcare, invasive fungal infections present ongoing hurdles for medical practitioners, particularly when dealing with critically ill individuals and those compromised in their immunity. The current estimation suggests a diverse fungal kingdom containing around 1.5 to 5 million species, with at least 300 known to cause infections in humans.⁽¹⁾

A fungal infection is an enormous danger to human health. Approximately 25% of people worldwide experience vulvovaginal candidiasis and cutaneous [skin] fungal infections. Moreover, individuals with immunosuppression or immunodeficiency, such as those with HIV infection, neutropenia, or cancer, have 50% mortality rate from systemic fungal infection.⁽²⁾

Top fungus killers include species of *Candida*. Among these, *Candida albicans* continues to be the most frequent source of systemic candidiasis, which can be fatal. Most people have *C. albicans* as a commensal, an opportunistic pathogen that frequently causes systemic and mucosal infections.⁽³⁾

There are two main types of fungi: moulds and yeasts. When it comes to mould colonies, the filamentous strands known as hyphae make up the colonies, while yeasts are usually single, small, oval cells. Certain fungi are dimorphic, meaning that they can exist as moulds or yeasts depending on the surrounding conditions (e.g. temperature).

The majority of fungi are widely distributed and can multiply effectively in their native habitats without the assistance of humans or other animals. However, certain species can cause superficial, subcutaneous, or systemic infections in humans, making them adventitious pathogens.⁽⁴⁾

- **Fungal Virulence:** Factors like melanin, fungal invasins (e.g., Als3), enzymes, and polysaccharides play roles in tissue invasion and neurotropism.
- **Host Immune Evasion:** Fungi modify host responses, affecting disease outcomes.
- **Clinical Perspective:** Understanding immune mechanisms and susceptibility factors informs immunotherapeutic options.⁽⁵⁾

The candidiasis can cause everything from mild surface infections to potentially fatal widespread illness. Oral, vaginal, and cutaneous candidiasis are the most common superficial infections. In addition of entering the bloodstream (candidemia), *Candida* species can infiltrate practically any organ in the body, leading to systemic or widespread candidiasis.⁽⁶⁾

Mortality and life-threatening mycoses are linked to the occurrence of fungal infections in patients with various illnesses, especially Covid-19. A range of severity levels of superficial, cutaneous, subcutaneous, mucosal, and systemic infections can be caused by fungi. *Candida* spp. is a part of the human microbiome and can cause invasive candidiasis, a potentially fatal infection, in people with impaired immune systems, such as those with HIV, cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy, and patients on immunosuppressive medications. Fungal pathogens like *Candida*, *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium*, *Mucorales*, and moulds can cause healthcare-associated infections (HAI) in individuals with underlying disorders in addition to opportunistic and systemic infections.⁽⁷⁾

Either an opportunistic organism that infects an at-risk host or an invasive organism that is endemic to a particular region can produce systemic fungal infections. Systemic infections are linked to a high rate of morbidity and mortality and have the potential to be fatal. It is challenging to pinpoint the precise incidence of systemic infections due to the difficulty of diagnosis and the fact that the causal agent is frequently only identified after death. Although *Aspergillus* species and *Candida albicans* are the most common infections, other fungus, such as non-*albicans Candida* spp., are becoming more and more significant.

Vaginal infection:

Any vaginal inflammation or infection is referred to as "vaginitis" generally.

Itching, dyspareunia, inflammation of the vulva and vagina, increased discharge, and foul-smelling vaginal discharge are among the symptoms. It has become most common in women.

Bacterial, fungal, or protozoal infections can cause vaginal infections. Another frequent cause of vaginitis is atrophy related to menopause. In order to determine the cause and start the proper therapy for a non-specific complaint of vaginal discharge or irritation, a clinical evaluation is necessary.^(8,9)

One of the most common gynaecologic problems is a vaginal discharge. These infections result in about 500 visits to each gynaecologist each year, making up about 7% of all patient visits to these doctors. Three types comprise the majority of instances of infectious vaginitis: non-specific vaginitis (NSV), accounting for 40–50% of cases; candidiasis, accounting for 20–30% of cases; and trichomoniasis, accounting for 20–30% of cases.

The patient typically experiences persistent symptoms after treatment, even though there don't seem to be

many causes of vaginitis. The inability to reduce symptoms can be attributed to a variety of factors. The most frequent ones are sexual reinfection, therapeutic

errors, and diagnosis errors. Drug resistance, decreased host immunity, and nonsexual recurrence are less frequent causes.⁽¹⁰⁾

MATERIALS:

Chemicals and reagents

Table: Chemicals and reagents

Sl. No.	Ingredients	Company name
1	Tolnaftate	Yarrow Chemicals PVT. Ltd, Mumbai, India
2	Bovine serum albumin	S D Fine Chem Ltd, Mumbai
3	4% w/v Glutaraldehyde	SD Fine Chemical Ltd, Mumbai, India.
4	PEG 400	Hi-Media Laboratories, Mumbai, India.
5	PEG 4000	Hi-Media Laboratories, Mumbai, India.
6	THEOBROMA OIL	Sigma Aldrich, USA
7	Sodium acetate	Central Drug House Pvt Ltd., New Delhi, India
8	Dialysis membrane	Hi-Media Laboratories, Mumbai, India.

METHODOLOGY:

Determination of Solubility of Tolnaftate

The qualitative solubility of Tolnaftate was determined using various solvents as given in the Table. 3 at room temperature.

Table. Solubility of tolinaftate in different solvents

SL.NO	SOLVENT
1	Ethanol
2	Acetone
3	Methanol
4	Chloroform
5	Acetate buffer 4.4

Calibration curve of Tolnaftate using UV- Visible spectroscopy.

Determination of absorption maxima (λ max)

By dissolving 10 mg of pure drug (Tolnaftate) in 100 mL of ethanol, a standard solution of tolinaftate was created. To achieve a concentration of 10 ppm, it was further diluted using water. This solution (main stock solution) had a concentration of 100 μ /ml. A 10ml volumetric flask containing 2ml of the aforesaid solution was filled with pH 4.4 acetate buffer to dilute it to a concentration of 20 μ g/ml (secondary stock solution). The secondary stock solution was divided into 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5ml volumetric flasks. The volume was then diluted with pH 4.4 phosphate buffer to obtain concentrations of 10, 20, 30,40, and 50 μ g/ml, respectively. The solution's spectrum was measured using a UV-visible spectrophotometer in the 200–400 m range. It was discovered that tolinaftate's λ max was 256 nm.

Drug-polymer compatibility studies by FT-IR spectroscopy

To identify interactions between drugs and polymers as well as physical mixtures of drugs and polymers, a study on drug polymer compatibility was conducted. Using a mortar and KBr at a ratio of one to one

hundred, the material was carefully triturated. A small amount of this sample combination was fed into a pellet maker, where it was compressed under a pellet press at a rate of 10 kg/cm² to create a pellet. In the Shimadzu FT-IR spectrophotometer, the pellet was scanned at 4000cm⁻¹ to 400cm⁻¹ while it was in a sample container. A compatibility study was conducted for drugs, polymers, and physical mixtures of polymers and drugs. In order to identify functional group peaks, the acquired spectra were compared and analyzed.⁽⁷⁴⁾

PREPARATION OF TOLNAFTATE LOADED NANOPARTICLES BY DE-SOLVATION METHOD

Tolnaftate loaded albumin nanoparticles were prepared by de-solvation method. Briefly, bovine serum albumin was weighed and dissolved in distilled water, solution kept under continuous stirring at 500 rpm at room temperature, then to bring the pH of the medication and polymer solution to about 10, 0.1N NaOH was created. Then tolinaftate was weighed and dissolved in acetone. Using a syringe, acetone was added to the medication and polymer solution after the pH was adjusted, causing turbidity to develop (whitish color) Then tolinaftate was weighed and added to this

above solution until the solution became turbid. This solution was stirred around 30 mins of constant stirring at 500 rpm, later 4% w/v of glutaraldehyde is added as a cross-linking agent, continued the stirring for 8-12 hr. nanosuspension was collected and centrifuged for 20 min at 20000 rpm to separate the nanoparticles.

After centrifugation the supernatant liquid was collected for unbound drug evaluation and the sediment was collected and freeze dried under vacuum to obtain the nanoparticles, which were stored for further characterisations.

Representation of preparation of Tolnaftate NPs

FORMULATION OF NANOPARTICLES: DE-SOLVATION METHOD

Table . Formula for preparation Tolnaftate loaded bovine serum albumin nanoparticles

Sl no	Formulation code	Drug (mg)	Polymer (mg)
1	F1	100	100
2	F2	100	200
3	F3	100	300
4	F4	100	400
5	F5	100	500

Preparation of suppositories

Suppositories were prepared by using Fusion method. The cocoa butter or mixed PEG's (PEG 400 and PEG 4000) used as a base certain amount of PEG 400 and PEG 4000 is taken, the base material is melted on a water bath or in a suitable container until it forms a clear liquid. In a same way cocoa butter is also taken and melted. It is important to melt the base gently to avoid degradation of heat-sensitive components. Submerge the molds in paraffin to facilitate easy removal of the suppositories from the mold. Once the base is completely melted, the active ingredient is

added to the liquid base. It is then thoroughly mixed to ensure uniform distribution of the active ingredient throughout the base material. The molten mixture is then poured into suppository molds. These molds are usually made of metal and are designed to give the suppositories their final shape and size. The filled molds are allowed to cool at room temperature or in a refrigerator until the suppositories solidify. This process involves the base material resolidifying around the active ingredient. Once the suppositories have hardened and taken shape, they can be removed from the molds. They are then inspected for quality

and packaged in suitable containers or foil wrappers to protect them from light and moisture.

FORMULATION OF SUPPOSITORIES: FUSION METHOD

Fig. Representation of preparation of suppositories loaded with TNF Nps

RESULTS:

Preparation of standard graph:

The standard graph of tolinaftate absorbance was measured at 256 nm by using UV- visible spectrophotometer.

Fig : Data for standard curve of tolinaftate in Ph 4.4 phosphate buffer.

Table : The standard curve data for tolinaftate was acquired in a pH 4.6 phosphate buffer at 256nm.

	Sample ID	Type	Conc	WL256.0
1	T1	Standard	10.000	0.217
2	T2	Standard	20.000	0.436
3	T3	Standard	30.000	0.652
4	T4	Standard	40.000	0.871
5	T5	Standard	50.000	1.097

Drug-polymer compatibility studies by FT-IR spectroscopy

Fig : FT-IR spectrum of tolinaftate

Fig. FT-IR spectrum of Bovine serum albumin

Fig . FT-IR spectrum of TNF AND BSA

Fig . FT-IR spectrum of TNF NPs

Preparation of TNF NPs

Five distinct batches were created using the De-solvation technique method, where the concentration of the polymer bovine serum albumin was altered while maintaining a constant level of the drug tolinaftate. Following preparation, the nanosuspension underwent centrifugation to remove the supernatant liquid, and subsequently, to obtain nanoparticles freeze-drying was performed.

Determination of percentage yield of TNF NPS**Table . Percentage yield of TNF NPs:**

Formulation	Percentage yield
T1	62.3%
T2	69%
T3	88.5%
T4	81.7%
T5	83%

Determination of % Drug loading of TNF NPs**Table . Data of % drug loading**

Formulation	% drug loading
T1	10.571%
T2	16.49%
T3	36.85%
T4	16.47%
T5	15.61%

Determination of differential scanning calorimetry

The thermal analysis of TNF and TNF- BSA NPs were determined by DSC-60 detector and found to be 124.60 & 121.45 °C

Fig . DSC STUDIES OF TNF**Fig 15 DSC STUDIES OF TNF -BSA NPs**

Determination of particle size

Particle size analysis of TNF NPs was conducted using the Malvern Zetasizer Nano-S90 nanoparticle analyzer. The measurements revealed particle sizes ranging from nm to nm, accompanied by polydispersity index (PDI) values varying between and, as depicted in Figures 16-21.

Fig . Particle size of TNF-BSA NPs (T1)

Fig . Particle size of TNF-BSA NPs (T2)

Fig. Particle size of TNF-BSA NPs (T3)

Fig . Particle size of TNF-BSA NPs (T4)

Fig. Particle size of TNF-BSA NPs (T5)

Determination of zeta potential

Fig. Zeta potential of TNF NPs

Surface morphology by Scanning electron microscopy

SEM studies were employed to investigate the surface morphology of the M3 formulation. The images in Figure 22 depict the morphology of serum albumin nanoparticles loaded with Tolnaftate, revealing spherical -shaped nanoparticles without any signs of aggregation.

Fig. SEM analysis TNF-BSA NPs

In-Vitro drug release studies of tolnaftate loaded bovine serum albumin nanoparticles

Table. Cumulative percentage drug release data of TNF-BSA NPs formulations

Sl no	Time in (hrs)	Pure drug	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5

1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0.25	3.391705	11.93548	13.18894	13.62212	12.59908	12.18433
3	0.5	4.043134	18.39585	16.21484	17.40811	13.74811	13.92829
4	1	5.272166	22.91041	18.56	21.89419	18.57558	15.50415
5	1.5	6.347189	27.97521	20.73346	27.05935	21.13659	16.47687
6	2	7.432442	36.53539	25.95908	31.62885	24.31124	17.88175
7	4	8.684608	44.07244	34.43309	36.81281	28.40959	21.30829
8	6	10.67659	52.6306	44.05843	41.71373	31.07189	26.46323
9	8	13.84894	56.25622	50.20065	48.26378	34.14516	29.9718
10	12	16.73871	63.76553	55.37696	53.34535	37.43051	34.3424
11	24	20.11687	70.95742	62.16719	58.01226	40.11871	36.52341

Fig. Cumulative percentage drug release profiles of TNF-BSA NPs formulations

Release kinetics

Release kinetics studies were conducted to grasp the underlying release mechanism and determine the optimal fit with a kinetic model. The In Vitro release data was analysed through different kinetic models including Zero order, first order, Higuchi model, and Korsmeyer-Peppas model, and the regression values for each model were tabulated. Figures from 24-27, T1 to T5 formulations provide detailed insights into the release kinetics of the formulations studied.

Table. Regression values for each of the kinetic model of TNF-BSA NPs formulations

Formulation code	Drug release kinetics			Korsmeyer-Peppas	
	Zero order(r^2)	First order(r^2)	Higuchi (r^2)	(r^2)	n
T1	0.7031	0.3112	0.9305	0.9398	0.2903
T2	0.7499	0.3417	0.9418	0.8483	0.261
T3	0.6812	0.2845	0.9138	0.9177	0.2384
T4	0.6149	0.2583	0.8655	0.8884	0.1952
T5	0.6958	0.292	0.9431	0.8232	0.1805

Figure. Zero order release kinetics of TNF-BSA NPs formulations

Figure. First order release kinetics of TNF-BSA NPs formulations

Figure. Higuchi release kinetics of TNF-BSA NPs formulations

Figure. koresmeyer-Peppas kinetics of MTZ-BSA NPs formulations

Antifungal activity: (Zone of inhibition)

Fig . Antifungal activity of TNF-BSA NPs

Table: Antifungal activity of given sample

Sample	Zone of inhibition (mm in diameter)
Nps	14
Drug	16
Control	14
Antibiotic	16

Preparation of Suppositories

Suppositories were prepared by using fusion method, this method involves melting the suppository bases (1) PEG 400 and PEG 4000 as a base, (2) cocoa butter as a base and mixing it with medication.

Optimization of suppositories containing TNF-BSA loaded NP's:

Table. Formulation table for effect of independent variables on Melting point and length of suppositories:

		Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Response 1	Response 2
Std	Run	A:PEG 400	B:PEG 4000	C:DRUG	Length	MP
		ml	mg	%	cm	deg C
4	1	75	75	3	5.1	54
6	2	75	25	5	2.6	41
1	3	25	25	3	3.5	41
2	4	75	25	3	2.8	42
13	5	50	50	4	4.1	47
12	6	50	50	4	4.2	47
10	7	50	50	4	4	48
5	8	25	25	5	3.6	42
3	9	25	75	3	4.7	54
8	10	75	75	5	5.2	53
7	11	25	75	5	4.8	55
11	12	50	50	4	4.2	47
9	13	50	50	4	4.1	48

Effect of independent variables on length

Table. ANOVA for selected factorial model

Response 1: Length

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	7.54	3	2.51	319.31	< 0.0001	significant
A-PEG 400	0.1013	1	0.1013	12.86	0.0071	
B-PEG 4000	6.66	1	6.66	845.87	< 0.0001	
AB	0.7813	1	0.7813	99.21	< 0.0001	
Curvature	0.0209	1	0.0209	2.66	0.1416	
Residual	0.0630	8	0.0079			
Lack of Fit	0.0350	4	0.0087	1.25	0.4170	not significant
Pure Error	0.0280	4	0.0070			
Cor Total	7.63	12				

Table. Fit Statistics

Std. Dev.	0.0887	R ²	0.9917
Mean	4.07	Adjusted R ²	0.9886
C.V. %	2.18	Predicted R ²	0.9758
		Adeq Precision	44.5172

Polynomial Equation

$$\text{Length} = +4.04 - 0.1125 * A + 0.9125 * B + 0.3125 * AB$$

Length

- ▲ Error estimates

Shapiro-Wilk test

W-value = 0.827
p-value = 0.161

A: PEG 400
B: PEG 4000
C: DRUG

- Positive Effects
- Negative Effects

Fig. 36

Effect of independent variables on melting point:

Table. ANOVA for selected factorial model

Response 2: MP

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	312.50	1	312.50	744.05	< 0.0001	significant
B-PEG 4000	312.50	1	312.50	744.05	< 0.0001	
Curvature	0.3769	1	0.3769	0.8974	0.3658	
Residual	4.20	10	0.4200			
Lack of Fit	3.00	6	0.5000	1.67	0.3232	not significant
Pure Error	1.20	4	0.3000			
Cor Total	317.08	12				

Table. Fit Statistics

Std. Dev.	0.6481	R²	0.9867
Mean	47.62	Adjusted R²	0.9854
C.V. %	1.36	Predicted R²	0.9772
		Adeq Precision	40.1510

Polynomial Equation

$$\text{Melting Point} = +47.75 - 0.2500 * A + 6.25 * B -$$

MP

▲ Error estimates

Shapiro-Wilk test

W-value = 0.771

p-value = 0.046

A: PEG 400

B: PEG 4000

C: DRUG

■ Positive Effects

■ Negative Effects

Fig. 37

Factor Coding: Actual

MP (deg C)
(adjusted for curvature)
● Design Points

Actual Factors

A = 50

B = 50

C = 4

Fig. 38

Factor Coding: Actual

MP (deg C)
(adjusted for curvature)

Design Points:

● Above Surface

○ Below Surface

41 55

X1 = A

X2 = B

Actual Factor

C = 4

3D Surface

Fig. 39

Table. *In-vitro* release data of suppositories containing TNF-BSA loaded NPs

Sl no	Time (hrs)	F1	F2	F3	F4
1	0	0	0	0	0
2	0.25	7.990783	8.912442	15.02304	21.29032
3	0.5	9.167465	11.48083	19.6894	40.02857
4	0.75	10.52101	14.61779	27.35023	50.65714
5	1	15.55539	15.99696	40.43134	70.60461
6	1.5	22.00313	24.13502	53.27189	88.71889
7	2	26.32028	27.2377	67.43502	93.64332
8	4	30.70608	32.82065	80.8129	93.7235
9	6	35.86129	38.06968	91	93.79539
10	8	44.65954	43.7459	91.14286	93.85899
11	12	55.18286	56.26783	91.27834	93.91429
12	24	66.00065	67.03982	91.31429	93.96129
13	36	70.71853	72.65143	91.34194	94
14	48	76.1224	79.80581	91.45346	94.21475

Fig . *In-vitro* release profiles of suppositories containing TNF-BSA loaded NPs

Determination of release kinetics:

Release kinetics studies were conducted to grasp the underlying release mechanism and determine the optimal fit with a kinetic model. The In Vitro release data was analysed through different kinetic models including Zero order, first order, Higuchi model, and Korsmeyer-Peppas model, and the regression values for each model were tabulated. Figures from 28-31, F1 to F4 formulations provide detailed insights into the release kinetics of the formulations studied.

Table . Regression co-efficient

Formulation code	Drug release kinetics			Korsmeyer-Peppas	
	Zero order(r^2)	First order(r^2)	Higuchi (r^2)	(r^2)	n
F1	0.7966	0.4114	0.9558	0.8973	0.3621

F2	0.8126	0.3954	0.9652	0.9272	0.3381
F3	0.3764	0.1928	0.6296	0.8281	0.2848
F4	0.2165	0.1088	0.4299	0.7565	0.1938

Figure. Zero order release kinetics of suppositories loaded TNF-BSA NPs formulations

Figure. First order release kinetics of suppositories loaded TNF-BSA NPs formulations

Figure. Higuchi release kinetics of suppositories loaded TNF-BSA NPs formulations

Figure. Koresmeyer-Peppas release kinetics of suppositories loaded TNF-BSA NPs formulations

STABILITY STUDIES

Stability studies was conducted for 0,1,2,3 months formulated were characterized for particle size , zeta potential and % cumulative drug

Months	Particle size (nm)	Zeta potential (Mv)	% Cumulative drug release
0	88.12	-24.4	85.59%
1	84.38	-26.8	88.22%
2	89.55	-23.7	83.87%
3	92.71	-23.2	82.68%

Stability studies at $\pm$ for a period of 3 months

Months	Particle size (nm)	Zeta Potential (mV)	% cumulative drug release
0	87.58	-22.1	84.73
1	85.66	-23.5	82.38
2	89.22	-22.03	82.22
3	90.39	-24.52	81.39

Stability studies at room temperature for a period of 3 months

CONCLUSION:

In the present study, an attempt was made to formulate and characterize the tolinaftate loaded serum albumin nanoparticles.

By using FT-IR spectrometer, drug polymer compatibility investigations of a chosen drug and polymer were conducted that there was no possible interaction between the selected drug and polymer.

TNF-BSA loaded nanoparticles and were prepared by desolvation technique method. The opted method was able to produce nanosized particles with a mean diameter of 76.88 ± 0.52 nm to 284 ± 0.73 nm with the PDI of 0.07877 ± 0.23 and zeta potential was found to be -32.81 ± 0.75 mV.

The synthesized nanoparticles showed that process yield ranged from $62 \pm 0.3\%$ to $83 \pm 0.1\%$ w/w and drug loading ranged from $10.0 \pm 0.5\%$ to $36.0 \pm 0.8\%$. Among the five batches of nanoparticles, nano formulation T3 selected as an ideal formulation by considering its drug loading 36.0% and particle size 82.49 ± 0.33 nm.

The in vitro release studies were carried out for all the batches. *In-vitro* studies showed that the drug release of the TNF-BSA NPs ranged from 36.52% to 70.9% at the end of 24hr in pH 4.4 acetate buffer.

Release kinetic studies of loaded nanoparticles indicated to have the best fit to Higuchi with the highest value of 0.9138. Korsmeyers-Peppas 'n' value was 0.2384 and therefore it followed fickian mechanism.

The ideal formulation T3 was further incorporated into the suppositories for better efficacy of TNF to provide the sustained release.

The in vitro release studies were carried out for all the batches. *In-vitro* studies showed that the drug release of the suppositories loaded with TNF-BSA NPs ranged from 76.12% to 94.21% at the end of 48hr in pH 4.4 acetate buffer.

Release kinetic studies of loaded nanoparticles indicated to have the best fit to Higuchi with the highest value of 0.9652. Korsmeyers-Peppas 'n' value was 0.3381 and therefore it followed fickian mechanism.

Optimization by using full factorial design which says that when the concentration of PEG 4000 is increased in the suppository formulation, both the melting point and length of the suppository increase. Conversely, decreasing the concentration of PEG 400 results in an increase in both the melting point and length. This dual influence of PEG 4000 concentration indicates that higher levels contribute to elevated melting points and longer suppositories, while reduced levels lead to a decrease in both melting point and length.

Hence, we can conclude that Suppositories loaded with TNF-BSA nanoparticles, they show sustained release and better targeting to the specific site.

REFERENCES:

1. Wiederhold NP. Emerging Fungal Infections: New Species, New Names, and Antifungal

- Resistance. Vol. 68, Clinical Chemistry. Oxford University Press; 2022. p. 83–90.
2. Zhang TY, Chen YQ, Tan JC, Zhou JA, Chen WN, Jiang T, et al. Global fungal-host interactome mapping identifies host targets of candidalysin. *Nat Commun* [Internet]. 2024 Feb 27;15(1):1757. Available from: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-024-46141-x>
 3. D'enfert C, Kaune AK, Alaban LR, Chakraborty S, Cole N, Delavy M, et al. The impact of the Fungus-Host-Microbiota interplay upon *Candida albicans* infections: current knowledge and new perspectives. 2020; Available from: <https://academic.oup.com/femsre/advance-article/doi/10.1093/femsre/uaa060/6000215>
 4. Garber G. An Overview of Fungal Infections. Vol. 61, *Drugs*. 2001.
 5. Pathogenesis of Fungal Infections in the Central Nervous System_ Host and Pathogen Factors in Neurotropism_ Current Fungal Infection Reports.
 6. Prieto-Granada CN, Lobo AZC, Mihm MC. Skin Infections. In: *Diagnostic Pathology of Infectious Disease*. Elsevier; 2018. p. 542–647.
 7. Reddy GKK, Padmavathi AR, Nancharaiyah Y V. Fungal infections: Pathogenesis, antifungals and alternate treatment approaches. Vol. 3, *Current Research in Microbial Sciences*. Elsevier Ltd; 2022.
 8. Duff M. Vaginitis.
 9. Paladine HL, Desai UA. Vaginitis: Diagnosis and Treatment [Internet]. Vol. 97. 2018. Available from: www.aafp.org/afphttp://www.aafp.org/afp/2018/0301/p321-s1.html.
 10. eschenbach1983. March 1983 - Volume 26 - Issue 1 : *Clinical Obstetrics and Gynecology* (lww.com)